

STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL LEADERSHIP STYLE OF MANAGERS AND ORGANIZATIONAL HEALTH IN SCHOOLS OF DIVANDARREH CITY IN THE ACADEMIC YEAR 2015-16

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Abstract:

The objective of this research was study of a structural equation model leadership style of managers and organizational health in schools of Divandarreh city in the academic year 2015-16. The research method is descriptive and correlation. Thus, 220 individuals under investigation which include administrators and teachers in the education & training of city Divandarreh city were selected as randomly stratified. The required data were gathered by using two questionnaires of Clark's leadership style (1991) and organizational health of Hoy and Foldman (1996) and were analyzed by Pearson correlation coefficient and structural equation model. Results suggested that there is meaningful relationship between leadership styles with organizational health. Results of structural equation model indicate the predicting leadership style with organizational health.

Keywords: leadership styles, organizational health, school managers

Introduction

In the current era has been proved that social institutions which are based on objective and conscious structure have a strong role in the development of the community. One of these organizations, according to sociologists and social analysts is education & training organization. Undoubtedly, these organizations are one of the most important structures of training and education in the community. Thus, guidance and leadership such organizations are important and sensitive. The importance and role of management in our country, which has large area, relatively good weather, geographical location and is rich of natural resources and potential human resources, is

more crucial than ever (Ahmadi and Bazrafshan, 2013). Meanwhile one of the important and effective issues in management schools process is organizational health which refers to a situation that facilitates growth and development of an organization and makes it possible reaching to goals. In healthy organizations, their members are dutiful, have high moral performance, network communications, are useful and open, and people love to come to their workplace and by working in this place, they feel proudly and satisfied (Alaghe mand, 2006).

The concept of organizational health firstly raised in the educational organizations. The study of research literature reveals that the concept of organizational health is used in these organizations for two reasons. First, because the organization is considered a social system where managers and employees each play a role so a healthy organization should reflect a social interaction between these key elements (Brans, 2008) and second because it is necessary for an organization to be effective to the actual specific tasks (Amirkhani, 2015). According to Clark, a healthy organization is both consistent innovators, has a high capacity for bearing internal and external crises and is able to move forward to the new level (Davis, 1991).

According to Leiden and Klyngl (2000), health organization is a completely new concept in the organization which includes the organization's ability to perform their duties effectively in line with growth and improvement of the organization. A healthy organization is a place that people want to stay and work there and effective and useful persons. Organizational health has a positive impact that in schools has more important (Mazlomi, 2010). In fact organizational health is not only including ability of the organization for doing duties effectively yet includes ability of the organization for consistent grow and improvement. Supervisors in the healthy organizations are pledged and loyal employees with high morale and performance and open communicational channel and high success. Also, Fourd noted that a healthy, communicational organization creates only in the shadow of a strong, wise and impassioned leader that has penetrated at all organizational levels (Hemmat, 2011).

Organizational health is affected by many factors that can be effective in achieving organizational goals and results to effectiveness of the organization and finally have performance in the efficiency of the organization (Sinder, 2000) that one of these items can be leadership style of managers in schools (Taghinasab et al, 2009). Management and leadership is a key element of the organization and community and educational management has a special place among managements. If education and training of each community is on top of all of society's issues, the educational management as well has a special position on the improvement and development of community (Ahmadi and Bazrafshan, 2013). In fact, integrate management of human

and material resources in order to achieve organizational goals are a way that is suitable to the community (Katrin, 2007).

Another point that is very important to mention is the manager's role as the main cause of health promotion in the school; in fact managers have some duties in schools that for doing them should understand clearly, organizational roles and interpersonal relations and school goals and try for providing requirements of school members and customers and organizational health at school (Mazlomi, 2010). In addition, according to surveys conducted in this area, there was not found a study which directly paid attention to test the relationship between these two variables. Also, previous researches have approved or rejected each other in the some instances.

Amirinasab conducted a research which dealt with the relationship between leadership style and organizational health of secondary school teachers of Chabahar city. Results indicated that generally organizational health status was assessed favor from the perspective of teachers. The results of the correlation coefficient between grammatical style and organizational health and participatory style and organizational health have a meaningful relationship. But there was no meaningful relationship between the style of delegating and organizational health. Stepwise regression analysis also showed that the most prediction from health organization is belonged to participatory leadership style.

Ahmadi and Bazrafshan (2013) assessed relationship between management styles with organizational health and job stress of employees. Results showed that there is reverse and meaningful between management style and organizational health, there is direct, and meaningful relationship between tasks oriented management style and organizational health. A reverse and meaningful relationship observed between variables of organizational health with job stress. And finally, the results of predictions indicate the power of forecasting of network management of relationship and rule for variables of organizational health and job stress.

Mazloomi and Shahtalabi (2011) in their research with title of relationship between transformational leadership style of managers and organizational health of elementary schools of Isfahan city concluded that there is meaningful relationship between leadership style of managers and all indexes of organizational health of elementary schools.

Abdollah and Arokiasami (2016) conducted a research with purpose of examine effects of school culture over organizational health of teachers of secondary schools in Malaysia. The results of the analysis of the findings showed that the culture of school has a positive and meaningful effect over organizational health. Abdollah and Arokiasami (2015) conducted a research about relationship between transformational

leadership style and organizational health of secondary school teachers in Malaysia. Results of this research suggested that transformational leadership style and organizational health have a positive and meaningful relationship with each other. Lee,

Park and Joo (2015) conducted a research with title of organizational health effects on behavioral intentions of customers in terms of leadership of middle managers. The results showed a significant effect of health on customer behavioral intentions. But the results showed that by adding leadership as a moderator variable of effects of exogenous variable or organizational health on the endogenous variable or behavioral intentions, there is no difference. It can be said that moderate variable of leadership has a neural role between two mentioned variables. Given the importance of the items listed for leadership style and organizational health, the main motivation in the study is that little researches has examined the relationship between these two variables together which increases the importance of this research. So we hope that this study will result in managers of schools and training and educating departments have a better understanding of leadership styles and its relationship with organizational health to thereby improve the relationship between teachers and school staff and students' academic achievement.

Methods

The method of research is correlation and in terms of data gathering is field one. The statistical community was consisted of all schools managers and teachers of Divandarreh city. Based on the inquiries, conducted by education and training department in this region, the number of managers and teachers is 550. According to the target population by using Morgan table 220 people were selected as samples by using simple random sampling.

For data collection two questionnaires of 30 item of Klark leadership style (1991) which consisted and three subscales, dictator leadership style (director), democrats (participatory) and assignor (non-directive) which participants should express in a range of 5 degrees (from ever to never) the amount of their success by using each of the statements. Organizational health questionnaire of Hoe and Foldman in 1996 had created in 7 dimensions of institutional integration, principal influence, consideration, maintenance, support resources, morale and academic emphasis, also this questionnaire consists of 44 items; participants should response to this questionnaire should in a 5 degree spectrum (from ever to never) express the extent of their agreement or disagreement by using each of these statements.

The content validity of tools was examined by 5 people of management masters and after modifications was confirmed. The reliability of tools in one guide study by using Cronbach's alpha test for leadership style questionnaires calculated as $\alpha=0.90$, and for organizational health questionnaire $\alpha=0.85$. In the following obtained information from descriptive and inferential statistics Pearson correlation coefficient and structural equation model analyzed in the level of $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

To develop and test analytical model Amos structural equation analysis has used. But before using this statistical tool to evaluate the severity and direction of correlation relationships between latent variables of research model Pearson correlation coefficient was used which its results has come in Table 1, it should be noted that Pearson coefficients only express the relationship between variables as casual and impure variable. This means that in these correlations the effect of other variables is not under control.

Table 1: The results of relationship between manager's leadership styles with Organizational health

Organizational Health		Variable
0.603	R	Leadership Styles
0.001	Sig	

The results of the study showed that there was positive and meaningful relationship between manager's leadership styles with organizational health that is, between manager's leadership styles with organizational health 0.603 there was positive and meaningful relationship.

This means that with the increasing desirability of the leadership style from the view of managers, it can be expected that organizational health increase and vice versa.

Structural equation model (SEM)

In this research based on theoretical framework, previously has considered a theoretical structure has considered, thus to test the construct validity and goodness of fit test structure by using Amos software with possession data variables structural model was tested.

Figure 1: Structural Equation Model variables of leadership style and organizational health

Table 2: Indicators structural equation model variables leadership style and organizational health

Row	Index		Value	Desired Value	Status
	Persian Equivalent				
1	Normalized Fit Index	(Nfi)	0.937	Equal To Or More Than 0.90	Optimal
2	Incremental Fit Index	(Ifi)	0.958	Equal To Or More Than 0.90	Optimal
3	Comparative Fit Index	(Cfi)	0.957	Equal To Or More Than 0.90	Optimal
4	The Root Mean Square Error Of Estimate	(Rmsea)	0.094	Less Than 0.1	Relatively Good
5	Chi Square Normalized	(Cmin.Df)	2.929	Less Than 3	Relatively Good

Table 2, indicates the fact that Indices Chi square to degrees of freedom CMIN.DF is equal to 2.929, relatively good, comparative fit index of NFI, IFI, CFI is more than 0.90 and RMSEA index are optimal and non-optimal respectively. That is, the study model has optimal fit and considered factor structure for it, is acceptable and in other words, data from the study partly supported the study and confirming the theoretical model.

Table 3: Model path coefficient and significance level

Variable	Path Coefficient	The Value Of T	Sig
Leadership Style---Organizational Health	0.65	5.942	0.001

According to the diagram depicted in Figure 1 it becomes clear that the leadership style has meaningful and positive effect on the education and training schools of Divandarreh. In other words, it is specified that with the level of error 0.001, the leadership style is effective on the organizational health of managers. The coefficient of determination organizational health showed that 0.45 from variance between the two variables is common.

Discussion and Conclusion

Leadership is a subject that has been proposed from many discussions and researches. And its root can be found from elementary management literature. Also, the organization's experts have defined specific procedures to apply the styles and special procedures. However, the organization is not limited to leadership, only. And leadership will not be the only way to success in the organization, as the organization and its structure are surrounded by special factors and phenomenon. One of the factors is that today itself is rich of literature regarding the health of organization.

Therefore, in this study, structural Equation Model leadership style and organizational health in city schools of Divandarreh investigated in academy year 2015-16. Initially, Pearson correlation test for results indicated that there is a positive and meaningful relationship between manager's leadership styles with health organization. The result of the research is consistent with findings Amiri Nasab (2014), the oppressed and loving the King (2011) and Abdullah and Arokiasamy (2016).

In explaining this hypothesis can be stated that today one of the main factors in the success of schools of all countries is organizational health. Several factors are contributing to the success and performances of schools. Some of these factors include: widespread support of parents and communities, mental-social space of environment, supportive environment for staff, trust in interaction and respect among teachers. However, principals' leadership behavior and organizational health is a key factor affecting the performance of schools. Teachers play an important role in the implementation of educational goals and from the other hand, by knowing the personality, attitudes, expectations and objectives of a particular person with different needs, that as managers can, by correct decisions and proper leadership style, help on implementing educational goals and promote organizational health on schools (Ahmadi and Bazrafshan, 2013).

Moreover, the results of structural equation modeling showed that leadership style has a significant impact on organizational health. In other words, it was found that the level of error of 0.001 percent leadership style is effective on organizational health of

managers. The value of effect was equal to standard beta 0.65. This means that if school administrators comply with all aspects of leadership style and plan for this purpose it is likely that this will make the 67 percent change in organizational health.

Also, determination coefficient between variable of leadership style on organizational health indicates that 45% of the variance between the two variables is common. This means that the internal market will explain 45% of organizational health. In other words, leadership style explains the value of organizational health. And the amount of unexplained variance may be due to a number of factors or other variables, including demographic variables which in this study its effect were not measured. In conclusion, there is a significant effect between leadership style and organizational health.

This result is consistent with results of Taghnasab et al (2014) which examined the relationship between leadership styles and organizational health in secondary schools, and Ahmadi and Bazrfeshan (2013), Mazlamomi and Shahtalabi (2011) and Amiri Nasab (2014). Therefore, the style of principal not only important in terms of working conditions and understanding its dynamics yet it predicts school organizational health, human tendency of teachers and their trust in colleagues and principal. The healthy manager has trusted teachers who believe in high standards; in these schools, the degree of confidence is high to manager and colleagues. Coordination of educational programs is the next step. Communication within the school is creative and coordination in the educational would contribute essentially at the performance of the educational institution (Ahmadi and Bazrafshan, 2013).

Results showed that there is positive and meaningful relationship between leadership styles with organizational health of schools managers of Divandarreh. So when school managers are using from a leadership styles which are simpler for them and are more appropriate with their personal features. We can conclude that leadership style in different workplaces is appropriate with organizational relations and school managers are an effective key factor in organizational health and finally on teacher's performance.

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